

Development of a Power Model for OCP Servers based on IPMI Data

Sibel Yilmaz^a, Mustafa Kuzay^a, Oguzhan Herkiloglu^b, Cagatay Yilmaz^c, Ender Demirel^{a*}

^aDesign and Simulation Tech. Inc., 26480, Eskisehir, Turkey

^b BitNet Information Services, Kastamonu Teknocity, 37000 Kastamonu, Turkey

^c RISE ICE Data Center, Björkskataleden 112, 973 47 Luleå, Sweden

*Corresponding author, edemirel@dstechs.net (E. Demirel).

Abstract: Estimation of the IT power consumption of a server by fans and CPUs is essential to the development of energy-aware IT management. Power consumption of a CPU can be essentially decomposed to static and dynamic parts. The former consists of idle and temperature dependent leakage power consumptions, the latter consists of workload dependent power consumption. In this study, a comprehensive experimental campaign was carried out at Empa data center to characterize power consumption of the OCP server. Server power consumption and temperature of each CPU were measured for various workloads and fan speeds via Prometheus. Temperature differences between two CPUs were found to increase when the fan speed reduced. Maximum CPU temperature and server power consumption dropped suddenly when the server utilization exceeded 0.5 due to the impact of hyper-threading. According to this observation, empirical equations were proposed for the prediction of the server power consumption considering fan speed, utilization rate and CPU temperature. Experimental tests indicated that the proposed server model could accurately predict power consumption of the OCP server taking into account the impact of hyper-threading.

Keywords: data center; OCP server; power model; CPU

1. Introduction

Server power modeling plays a vital role in optimizing energy usage, reducing costs, enhancing performance, and contributing to environmental sustainability in the realm of data centers, cloud computing, and modern computing systems. Demands for computing and cooling power have increased rapidly with the developing technology in recent years. For this reason, it is very important to understand the relationship between computing power, temperature, leakage and cooling power to ensure energy efficiency in data centers. Zapater et al. [1] proposed an empirical model for the leakage component by monitoring separately the computing and cooling power consumption in a server and experimentally examining the temperature-leakage-energy changes. Zapater et al. [2] developed empirical models by analyzing the interactions between temperature, leakage and cooling power to predict static and dynamic power consumption in servers. As a result, incorporating leakage power into the workload and cooling management provided additional energy savings, although it had no effect on performance. Ham et al. [3] developed a server model that takes into account server

thermal characteristics, including server power, fan airflow, and exhaust temperature based on CPU utilization and temperature. Mirhoseini-Nejad et al. [4] proposed a simple optimization algorithm that both model server power consumption and takes thermal models into calculation. The proposed algorithm not only assigns the workload but also adjusts the cooling unit setpoint accordingly. Sarkinen et al. [5] analyzed a system that synchronizes cooling unit fans and server fans to minimize energy use. Experimental studies are performed in a server wind tunnel. It is controlled via individual PID controllers to maintain a prescribed pressure drop across the server as air enters at a specific temperature and humidity. Experiments examine the impact on temperature difference while determining server operating temperature ranges that best balance server fan power versus power losses.

2. Power Model for OCP Servers at Empa

Power consumption of a server can be represented as the summation of CPU power and cooling power by the fan:

$$p^{server} = p^{IT} + p^{fan} \quad (1)$$

CPU power can be represented by the summation of the idle power, dynamic CPU power depending on the CPU load and leakage power depending on the CPU temperature:

$$p^{IT} = p^{idle} + p^{CPU,dyn} + p^{CPU,leakT} \quad (2)$$

3. IPMI Test

Experimental studies were conducted on the OCP server located at Empa data centers for different workloads and fan speeds. An OpenFoam case was designed with parallel computing to generate workloads for various CPU utilizations. The service developed in the present study can adjust fan speeds as fan duty cycle (FDC). Workloads were submitted to the server using the SLURM job scheduler. Each experimental test was carried out during 10 min with a sampling ratio of 10 sec to calculate time averaged data for the corresponding conditions. It was observed from the experimental data that the system stabilized after 3 min. Experimental studies conducted in the present study took almost 2 days considering waiting durations between each test to exclude transient effects on the experimental data. An experimental study was first carried out at idle condition to determine idle power consumption. Then, experimental studies were conducted for various workloads and fan speeds for the development of an empirical model.

3.1 IPMI Test at Idle Condition

An experimental study was conducted using various fan speeds at idle condition. Power consumption and temperature of each CPU temperature was measured and listed in the following table.

Table 1

Variation of the power consumption and CPU temperature with the fan speed at idle condition.

FDC (%)	P _{server} (W)	T _{CPU-1} (°C)	T _{CPU-0} (°C)
1	69.00	38.50	35.00
10	69.00	34.53	31.47
20	69.00	32.22	39.68
30	69.00	30.46	28.76
40	71.90	29.44	28.14
50	72.51	28.71	27.64
60	75.36	28.25	27.32
70	80.90	27.78	27.00
80	86.80	27.31	26.68
90	92.90	27.25	26.63
100	101.69	27.39	26.78

3.1.1. Fan Power Consumption

Power consumption of a single fan is 25.2 W at a maximum rpm (9200) from the specification of the fan on the OCP Leopard V1 server model [6]. Power consumption of the fans can be calculated using the following fan law:

$$\frac{P}{P_{max}} = \left(\frac{rpm}{rpm_{max}} \right)^3 \quad (3)$$

Fan power consumptions are calculated from Eq. (3) for two fans and listed in Table for different fan speeds. As the leakage power consumption is negligible when the fan speed is maximum, the idle power consumption is determined as 51.6 W.

Table 2

Variation of the power consumptions of fan and leakage.

FDC (%)	P _{server} (W)	T _{CPU-1} (°C)	P _{fan,law} (W)	P _{CPU,leakT} (W)
1	69.00	38.50	35.00	17.40
10	69.00	34.53	31.47	17.35
20	69.00	32.22	39.68	17.10
30	69.00	30.46	28.76	16.04
40	71.90	29.44	28.14	17.07
50	72.51	28.71	27.64	14.61
60	75.36	28.25	27.32	12.87
70	80.90	27.78	27.00	12.01
80	86.80	27.31	26.68	9.39
90	92.90	27.25	26.63	4.46
100	101.69	27.39	26.78	-0.31

3.2 IPMI Test for Various Fan Speeds and Workloads

Experimental studies were conducted for different fan speeds and workloads. Temperature differences between CPUs are calculated and plotted with respect to the utilization rate for different fan duty cycles in the following plot. The temperature difference was found to increase when the fan speed reduces.

Fig. 1. Variations of the CPU temperature differences with utilization rate for different fan speeds.

Variations of the maximum CPU temperature with the FDC are plotted in the following figure. The maximum CPU temperature drops when the utilization rate exceeds 0.5 due to the impact of hyper-threading on the processors.

Fig. 2. Variations of the maximum CPU temperature with the utilization rate for various fan speeds.

Variations of the server power consumption with the utilization rate for different fan speed speeds are shown in the following figure. Power consumption dropped suddenly due to the impact of the hyper-threading on processors.

Fig. 3. Variations of the server power consumption with the utilization rate for various fan speeds.

3.2.1. CPU Power Consumption

The CPU power consumption can be calculated from Eq. (2) including idle, dynamic and leakage power consumptions. This idle power was determined as 51.6 W from the previous experimental study at idle condition. Dynamic power consumption can be estimated as the linear variation with respect to the utilization rate u :

$$P^{CPU,dyn} = c_1 u_{cpu} \quad (4)$$

Where c_1 is the empirical coefficient and u_{cpu} is the utilization rate of the CPU. The following Taylor series expansion can be used for the prediction of the leakage power since the leakage power varies exponentially with temperature:

$$P^{CPU,leakT} = c_2 + c_3 T_{cpu} + c_4 T_{cpu}^2 \quad (5)$$

Thus, the CPU power consumption can be estimated using the following equation:

$$P^{IT} = c_0 + c_1 u_{cpu} + c_2 + c_3 T_{cpu} + c_4 T_{cpu}^2 \quad (6)$$

Where $c_0=51.6$. Experimental studies were conducted for different CPU loads and fan speeds. Then, empirical coefficients are calculated and listed in the following table.

$$P^{server} = c_0 + c_1 u_{cpu} + c_2 + c_3 T_{cpu} + c_4 T_{cpu}^2 + P_{fan} \quad (7)$$

Table 3

Empirical coefficients according to the hyper-threading.

uCPU	c0	c1	c2	c3	c4
$0 < u \leq 0.5$	51.6	263.8868	-38.5184	3.8138	-0.0269
$0.5 < u < 1$	51.6	221.19235	-138.9345	4.2665	-0.0281

Maximum and average prediction errors of the proposed coefficients were calculated and listed in the following table. The calculated errors between measured and predicted values proved the accuracy of the proposed equations.

Table 4

Error statistics.

u_{CPU}	Max. Error (%)	Average Error (%)
$0 < u \leq 0.5$	5.85	1.36
$0.5 < u < 1$	2.58	1.08

An additional experimental study was carried for $u=0.64$ under various fan speeds to test accuracy of the proposed equations for a given workload. Maximum and average errors were calculated as 7.77% and 4.41%.

Table 5

Comparison of measured and predicted power consumptions for $u=0.64$.

Measured Data			Calculated Data			Server Power Model Results		
FDC (%)	P_{server} (W)	T_{CPU} (°C)	P_{fan} + $P_{CPU, idle}$	$P_{CPU, dyn}$ + $P_{CPU, leakT}$	P_{fan}	$P_{CPU, dyn}$ + $P_{CPU, leakT}$	P_{server}	Error (%)
10	215.30	66.70	51.65	163.65	0.05	162.790	214.441	0.399
20	214.32	61.95	52.00	162.32	0.40	159.700	211.703	1.222
30	212.34	52.41	52.96	159.38	1.36	149.659	202.620	4.577
40	209.29	48.31	54.83	154.46	3.23	143.770	198.595	5.109
50	210.41	45.68	57.90	152.51	6.30	139.501	197.401	6.181
60	215.44	43.80	62.49	152.95	10.89	136.205	198.692	7.774
70	216.76	42.88	68.89	147.88	17.29	134.530	203.418	6.157
80	222.51	41.49	77.40	145.10	25.80	131.897	209.301	5.936
90	229.42	40.92	88.34	141.08	36.74	130.773	219.114	4.494
100	236.90	40.27	102.00	134.90	50.40	129.495	231.495	2.281

4. Conclusions

Estimation of the server power consumption plays a critical role in the development of energy-aware workload assignment algorithms to minimize IT power consumptions in a data center. A series of experimental studies were conducted on an OCP server using various fan speeds and server utilizations to measure server power consumption and CPU temperatures from the Prometheus data monitoring system. It was found from the experimental data that the CPU temperature and server power consumption dropped suddenly when the server utilization exceeded 0.5 due to the impact of hyper-threading. Accordingly, an empirical model was proposed for the prediction of the server power consumption considering fan speed, server utilization and CPU temperature. This model can be reliably used while minimizing IT energy consumption in the energy-aware workload assignment framework, which can be integrated to the Kubernetes job scheduler.

Acknowledgements

This paper is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 956059.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Nomenclature

$P_{CPU,dyn}$	CPU Dynamic Power (W)
$P_{CPU,leakT}$	Temperature based Leakage Power (W)
P_{fan}	Fan Power (W)
P_{server}	Server Power (W)
T	Temperature (°C)
T_{CPU}	CPU temperature (°C)
u_{CPU}	CPU Utilization Rate
CPU	Central Processing Unit
FDC	Fan Duty Cycle (%)
IT	Information Technology
OCP	Open Compute Project

References

- [1] Zapater, M., Ayala, J. L., Moya, J. M., Vaidyanathan, K., Gross, K., Coskun, A. K. (2013, March). Leakage and temperature aware server control for improving energy efficiency in data centers. In 2013 Design, Automation & Test in Europe Conference & Exhibition (DATE) (pp. 266-269). IEEE.
- [2] Zapater, M., Tuncer, O., Ayala, J. L., Moya, J. M., Vaidyanathan, K., Gross, K., Coskun, A. K. (2014). Leakage-aware cooling management for improving server energy efficiency. *IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems*, 26(10), 2764-2777.
- [3] Ham, S. W., Kim, M. H., Choi, B. N., Jeong, J. W. (2015). Simplified server model to simulate data center cooling energy consumption. *Energy and Buildings*, 86, 328-339.
- [4] Mirhoseini-Nejad, S. M., Badawy, G., Down, D. G. (2018, July). EAWA: Energy-aware workload assignment in data centers. In 2018 International Conference on High Performance Computing & Simulation (HPCS) (pp. 260-267). IEEE.
- [5] Sarkinen, J., Brännvall, R., Gustafsson, J., Summers, J. (2020, July). Experimental analysis of server fan control strategies for improved data center Air-based thermal management. In 2020 19th IEEE Intersociety Conference on Thermal and Thermomechanical Phenomena in Electronic Systems (ITherm) (pp. 341-349). IEEE.
- [6] Delta Electronics Inc., "Specification for approval" FMBG-ES Form 001, June, 2009.